

INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN MUSIC EDUCATION

Azizov Umidjon Sobir ugli

Republican specialized music school named after R. Glier

Deputy Director of Vocational Education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10653679>

Abstract: This article examines the issues of modern music education in the text of integration processes, synthesizes the experience of applying the principles of complex, systematic and interdisciplinary approaches to the main stages of formation of XX musical education. It is intended for the further development and experimental introduction of high and middle level pedagogues to the pedagogical process; ideas are presented as educational material in music pedagogy courses and special methods.

Key words: Integrative education, music pedagogy, methodology, culture, integrative approach, integrativism.

Introduction:

At the current stage of the development of music pedagogy, it is becoming more and more important to bring the complex and uncertain processes of updating and reorganizing the content of the existing system of training and education of musicians to the most optimal solution. The current level of music education in Belarus, one of the European countries, requires a scientific analysis and generalization of the possibilities of experimental directions in the educational work describing the creative and scientific-research activities of teachers of various music institutions. This task is important after the uneven development of individual aspects and links of educational and musical-pedagogical systems in various specific historical situations and the need for their coordination and coordination. The most advanced and scientifically-based way to change the system of training musicians in order to more closely connect the educational process with real practical activity is not only a highly qualified performer, but also a theoretically qualified and practically trained musician-teacher is to combine the content of education that allows to educate.

The main part.

Researches of leading scientists are devoted to the problems of quality training of teachers in the field of music education: including European and Russian specialists B. L. Yavorsky, L. A. Barenboym, A. D. Alekseeva and others. The idea of integration appeared in the depths of politics and economics, where it is used in its most clear and noble sense. At the same time, it is one of the most promising and advanced methods of solving problems in the modern world community. Integration is a process that leads to the emergence of a number of common properties, new properties of different elements.

Integration processes have long been effective in economic and financial education, network sciences and university school. Similar problems have arisen in front of music and pedagogic science. They need not only performing musicians, but also scientific musicians who are able to raise music pedagogy to a new level, who are able to introduce new ideas in teaching. the teacher includes a tendency to provide full training of musicians.

Scholars cite an excellent and still relevant definition of a teacher-musician: "only musicians should teach, not voice teachers."

In fact, there is a significant gap between the development of advanced pedagogic science and the actual methodological level of the wide practice of teaching at primary and secondary levels - music schools and music colleges. The reason for this is the inconsistency of the level of preparation of the graduates of music universities for pedagogical activity, which is often focused only on performance, not on teaching. A paradox arises: on the one hand, a highly literate, intellectually developed musician emerges from the walls of the university, whose views, assessment criteria, performance repertoire are close to the ideal of "listening load", knowing the goals and tasks of his pedagogical work; on the other hand, when he comes to work at a music college, he faces unique individual problems in working with students, feels unprepared for many tasks, and as a result loses confidence in himself as a teacher and fulfills his creative needs performance, in rare cases - tries to focus on the work of the choirmaster. There are many new methodological developments in local and world pedagogy that help update the content of musical education, and in everyday life, approaches that are increasingly ineffective and expedient in terms of today's requirements are still very difficult. The idea of combining educational content is best suited to the tasks of temporary pedagogy. When we talk about the fundamentalization of the training of a musician's teacher, the inclusion of meaningful and reasonable connections in its context, tasks such as solving the problems of the formation of the musician-teacher's personality appear. According to some researchers, the process of integration is a unifying process based on the development of relationships between elements aimed at effective achievement of goals. This process is related to the formation of a whole system and strengthening of its unity [2, p. 157].

Integration in the field of music education is a phenomenon that includes the experimental scientific and practical work experience of the past years. The closest integration is the idea of a comprehensive approach to education, its goal is to connect various components of education and upbringing, to introduce various complex courses into the curriculum, interdisciplinary research and practical developments, close to the main specialty connection with science and others. In the process of development and implementation, the integrated approach to education has achieved positive results in a number of universities, in the work of leading teachers in the past, but it has never turned into a holistic educational system. The disadvantage of the development of these ideas is that the main goal of this method was to connect different components of musical education, but the specific characteristics of the connections and the elements they combine were not defined. The experience of developing and implementing the complex method had its positive and negative sides, which undoubtedly influenced the passing of these ideas into the background, their insignificance at the current stage of the development of musical education. Nevertheless, the generalization of the experience of the leading teachers of the past, related to the most advanced idea of the integrated approach to education and training, will restore the general picture of the state of musical education and reveal new promising ways of its development. made it possible to give, which was manifested in the interdisciplinary approach that is being actively implemented today.

The idea of an integrative process in the process of musical education to train not only a performing musician, but also a teaching musician has ancient roots in the history of musical education. In the first conservatories founded by the brothers Anton and Nikolai Rubinstein,

great attention was paid to the pedagogical direction and the requirements for its level were quite high. Therefore, graduates have created strong music schools in the regions that train professionals and amateurs. Musical education received a new impetus in the early 20s, at the initiative of B. L. Yavorsky.

The seriousness of the attitude to ensure the content of the teacher-musician's professional training is fully practice-oriented is confirmed by the period of education.

In pre-school educational institutions and schools, general musical education is actually considered as an organization that carries out the main work activity in the process of training pedagogic personnel, and lessons are organized accordingly.

Music departments and faculties were opened much later - in the late 1940s and early 1950s - in several pedagogical educational institutions.

The profiling of music teachers of the 20th century and still exists today (training of personnel for music schools and art schools - in music colleges, for music colleges - in music academies and conservatories), the minimum knowledge received by students in the complex of general musical pedagogical direction and turned out to be limited in skills. The situation became more acute when the instructional pedagogic departments and faculties of music schools and conservatories were abolished. In the post-war period, there is a rapid growth of children's music schools in urban and rural areas; this required the opening of music schools in small towns with a very modest musical life, culture, lack of teachers and insufficient material base, which sometimes led to an increase in the number of music universities that were opened without sufficient strength and personnel. There is a clear inconsistency between the internationally recognized highest level of local music art and education and the unsatisfactory state of daily life of peripheral music educational institutions, which is due to the low quality of the work of trained musicians-teachers in such conditions and was related to efficiency.

In the 70s, a gradual revival of scientific-pedagogical thought and social activity in the field of musical education was observed. In 1972, Professor L. A. Barenboim at the Leningrad Conservatory justified the need for pedagogization of local music education as the main factor for the further development and distribution of musical art types. This thesis was discussed and accepted at several scientific and methodical conferences held in his name at the State Institute of Music. At the opening of the Tbilisi conference in 1980, Professor A. D. Alekseev noted that in the last 10-15 years, many musicians have sought to solve the problem of improving the training of musical and pedagogical personnel. And so far this task has not been fully resolved.

New concepts have appeared in modern pedagogy: "integrativism", "integrative approach", objective factors that help to introduce the ideas of integration into the wide practice of pedagogical activity are analyzed, the importance of parts, their characteristics are determined, which makes them organic with other parts "integrated education". Increasingly, scientists are raising the issue of technological support for the integration process in pedagogy.

A. Ya. Daniluk rightly notes that the saturation of science with more and more knowledge of various origins makes it a task to adopt effective countermeasures that allow to provide a synthetic perception of this knowledge: both practical problems in the educational process, solving both scientific and theoretical problems, wide use of cybernetic machines in the educational process, active use at all stages of education are methods that ensure the

instillation of skills for independent learning [3]. Pedagogical process, according to leading teachers, is aimed at developing the experience of education itself, using different forms of lessons (individual, individual group, open lessons, master classes, concert and pedagogical practice, etc.), theoretical and practical training should be directed to synthesis. It is also important to consider the psychological and pedagogical issues of promoting professional musical activity, which were fundamentally developed in the works of V. L. Yakonyuk [4].

Issues of educational integration N. A. Gorelik believes that the task of forming the personal structure of students is possible only in the conditions of combining all their activities [5].

The task of developing the ability of modern students not only to acquire knowledge, but also to integrate knowledge remains the most urgent in the era of rapid development of information technologies. In the field of musical creative skills, the integration of knowledge in the field of information technology is very relevant, it encourages students to develop creative skills, forms the need for personal and creative self-awareness.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be noted that in accordance with today's trends, there is a need to search for a pedagogical model of integration, to rely on new principles of teaching, the need to take them into account requires time. The research of leading scientists in the field of pedagogical activity indicates the search for different ways to solve this problem. Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- modern research in this field is based on the significant experience of previous scientific developments based on the ideas of interdisciplinary and complex relations;
- scientific research considers both the general theoretical problems of integration and the integration of scientific knowledge in various fields of science and applied sciences;
- there was a need for a deeper, innovative study of the entire spectrum of musical education problems in each specific musical specialty, based on the achievements of modern pedagogic science.

References:

1. Tsvinskaya, N. P. On the integration of musical theoretical knowledge in the piano class and the nature of authentic performance / N. P. Tsvinskaya: materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference, 2003. - P. 101-105.
2. Levchenko, V.V. Integration processes in pedagogical science / V.V. Levchenko // Bulletin of SamSU. - 2007. - No. 5/1(55). - pp. 157-165.
3. Danilyuk, A. Ya. Theoretical and methodological foundations of designing integral humanitarian educational spaces: dissertation... Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences / A. Ya. Danilyuk. - Rostov-on-Don, 2001. - 347 p.
4. Yakonyuk, V. L. Musician. Need. Activities / V. L. Yakonyuk. - Minsk, 1993. - 147 p.
5. Gorelik, N.A. Pedagogical integration of artistic and cognitive activities as a condition for the general development of junior schoolchildren: dissertation of a candidate of pedagogical sciences / Gorelik Nadezhda Aleksandrovna. - Moscow, 2010. - 221 p.

6. Pivovarova, O. V. Current problems of modern music education / # O. V. Pivovarova / / Current problems of music pedagogy: collection of scientific works. Vol. VI. - Saratov, 2013. - pp. 162-169.
7. Kharatova, S. K. (2021). Strategic issues of improving spiritual and educational activities in the republic of uzbekistan. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(11), 313-320.

